

Alkylation in Presence of Potassium Fluoride

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The effect of potassium fluoride on the alkylation of several malonic esters with benzyl chloride has been studied.

Phthalimidomalonic ester is an intermediate in the synthesis of a number of *alpha*-amino acids. The necessary alkylation of the ester involves prior preparation of the dry sodium salt^{1,2,3,4}. To obviate this, we have effected the benzylation of diethyl phthalimidomalonate in presence of potassium carbonate with dimethylformamide (DMF) as solvent in good yields⁵.

The catalytic activity of potassium fluoride in decarboxylation reaction was discovered by Nesmeyanov⁶ during an attempted preparation of trifluoroacetic acid from trichloroacetic acid. Subsequently, potassium fluoride has also been utilized as a catalyst in a series of addition-dehydration reactions of active methylene compounds⁷. The catalytic activity has been attributed to the capacity of metal fluorides to form hydrogen bond with protic acids. In recent years Rand and coworkers⁸ have studied the catalytic activities of a number of metal fluorides in Knoevenagel reaction. The hydrogen bonded intermediates have been postulated by Rand as shown:

Pursuant to our work on alkylation with dimethylformamide as solvent (*loc. cit.*), it was considered of interest to study whether potassium fluoride could similarly catalyse the alkylation of active methylene groups.

Diethylmalonate and benzyl chloride reacted smoothly in presence of equivalent amount of potassium fluoride and potassium carbonate to afford diethyl benzylmalonate in 64% yield, based on diethylmalonate consumed (about 30% unconsumed malonic

1. Sorenson, *Chem. Zentr.*, 1903, 11, 33.
2. Barger and Weichselbaum, *Organic Syntheses*, Coll. Vol. II, 1943, 384.
3. Dunn and Smart, *ibid.*, Coll. Vol. IV, 1963, 55.
4. Wagner and David, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1966, **88**, 7.
5. Sen and Sarma, *This Journal*, 1967, **44**, 644.
6. Nesmeyanov *et. al*, *Akad. Nauk. S. S. S. R. Otdel. Khim. Nauk, Izvestiya*, 1948, 240.
7. Aoyama *et al.*, *J. Sci. Res. Inst.* (Japan), 1958, **52**, 99.
8. Rand *et al.*, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1966, **31**, 1273, and earlier papers.

ester was recovered). Use of 0.5 molar excess of benzyl chloride effected no significant change in the yield of the product. Similarly, diethyl acetamidomalonate afforded diethyl acetamidobenzylmalonate in 75% yield.

However, when a similar reaction of benzyl chloride was carried out with diethyl phthalimidomalonate, a compound was obtained having a melting point significantly higher than that of the desired diethyl phthalimidobenzylmalonate. The compound on saponification afforded an acid melting at 158-160°, which on simultaneous decarboxylation and dehydration yielded *N*-phthalyl- β -phenylalanine⁵. From the analysis of the compound it was apparent that KF-catalysed opening up of the imide ring has occurred concomitantly, leading to the formation of the triethyl ester of benzyl *o*-carboxy benzamido malonic acid (I). The compound (I) on being heated at 240-245° or in boiling diphenyl oxide transformed into diethyl phthalimidobenzylmalonate (II) with elimination of ethanol.

In contrast with diethyl phthalimidobenzylmalonate, phthalimide, however, when similarly treated with potassium fluoride and potassium carbonate in refluxing ethanol, remained unchanged.

In all the experiments, an equivalent amount of potassium fluoride was used when needed and benzyl chloride was distilled prior to use.

EXPERIMENTAL

Diethyl benzylmalonate: A mixture of diethylmalonate (0.5 mole, 80 g.), anhydrous potassium carbonate (0.38 mole, 53 g.) and anhydrous potassium fluoride (0.5 mole, 29 g.) in dry ethanol (400 ml.) was heated to reflux with stirring and benzyl chloride (0.5 mole, 63 g.) was added. After heating for 8 hrs., the mixture was cooled, filtered and the solid

washed with ethanol. The filtrate and washings were combined and ethanol was removed by distillation. The residue was treated with water and extracted with chloroform. Chloroform was removed and the residue was distilled under reduced pressure. There was collected unreacted diethyl malonate (25 g., 31%), and 55 g. (64% based on malonic ester consumed) of diethyl benzylmalonate, b.p. 150-160° 7 mm.

Hydrolysis of a portion of the compound essentially as described in *Organic Syntheses*⁹ afforded benzylmalonic acid melting at 116-117°. The reported melting point is 117°¹⁰.

Diethyl acetamidobenzylmalonate: (a) Anhydrous potassium carbonate (0.23 mole, 31.5 g.) and anhydrous potassium fluoride (0.30 mole, 17.4 g.) was added to a solution of ethyl acetamidomalonate (0.30 mole, 65.1 g.) in dry ethanol (400 ml.) and heated with stirring. Benzyl chloride (0.35 mole, 43.5 g.) was added and heated under reflux. After two hours an additional amount of benzyl chloride (10 g.) was added and the heating was continued for six hours longer. The mixture was worked up essentially as described above, excess benzyl chloride being removed from a steam bath under reduced pressure. Yield, 46.7 g. (75%). On recrystallisation from a large volume of water the compound melted at 106°. Melting point and mixed melting point determination with a sample prepared according to Albertson *et al.*¹¹ showed no depression.

(b) Benzyl chloride (0.054 mole, 6.8 g.) was added with stirring to a solution of diethyl acetamidomalonate (0.05 mole, 10.8 g.) in dimethylformamide (50 ml.) containing anhydrous potassium carbonate (0.038 mole, 5.2 g.) and heated under reflux. After an hour, an additional amount of benzyl chloride (2.3 g.) was added and heating continued for 4 hours longer. Solvent was removed under reduced pressure. The residue was triturated with ice and recrystallised from water (yield, 12 g.; 78%), m.p. 105-106°.

The compound prepared by different methods have superimposable infra red spectra.

Triethyl ester of o-carboxybenzamido benzylmalonic acid (I): (a) Diethyl phthalimidomalonate was reacted with benzyl chloride essentially as described for the preparation of diethyl acetamidobenzylmalonate. On recrystallisation from ethanol the compound melted at 118° (yield, 11.5 g., 52%). (Found: C, 65.65; H, 6.63, C₂₄H₂₇O₇N requires C, 65.23; H, 6.15%)

(b) A mixture of diethyl phthalimidobenzylmalonate (198 mg.) and anhydrous potassium fluoride (50 mg.) in absolute ethanol (7 ml) was heated under reflux for 32 hrs. Ethanol was removed, the residue was treated with water and extracted with ether. Removal of ether left a viscous mass, which was crystallised from ethanol, yield, 180 mg (80%), m.p. 117-118°. Mixed melting point determination with a sample prepared as above recorded no depression.

The compound was saponified to give o-carboxybenzamido malonic acid, m.p. 158-162° and decarboxylated with simultaneous dehydration as described to give

9. C. S. Marvel, *Organic Syntheses*, Coll. Vol. III. 1955, 705.

10. Conrad, *Ber.*, 1905, **38**, 2738.

11. Albertson and Archer, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, **67**, 309.

N-phthalyl- β -phenylalanine.⁵ The melting point and mixed melting point determination with an authentic sample recorded no depression.

Diethyl phthalimidobenzylmalonate (II): The above triethyl ester was heated in boiling diphenyl oxide for 45 mins. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure, when the residue, on crystallisation from ethanol, melted at 109°. Mixed melting point determination with an authentic sample recorded no depression.

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